

ANALYTICAL CHEMISTRY OF THORIUM. PART X. AMMONIUM FUROATE (PYROMUCIATE) AND SODIUM SULPHANILATE

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Two new reagents, ammonium furoate and sodium sulphanilate, have been investigated and recommended for the estimation and separation of thorium from the rare earths. The first functions in the p_H above 2.0, estimates as little as 2.2 mg. of ThO_2 and frees in one precipitation thorium from fifty-fold excess of cerite earth oxides. The second functions in the p_H above 2.3; estimates as small as 1 mg. of ThO_2 and frees similarly from a 100-fold excess of cerite earth oxides. Both the reagents have been used to estimate thorium in monazite.

Furoic acid has been recommended for its valuable qualities by Kellog and Kellog (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1934, 6, 251) as an acidimetric standard. It is now observed that the acid possesses the property of precipitating thorium leaving the rare earths in solution. The thorium recovery is incomplete against the acid, but when the acid is neutralised with ammonia or better still, when its ammonium salt is employed, complete precipitation of thorium as well as separation from the trivalent rare earths in fifty-fold excess takes place from solutions of p_H above 2.0.

Sulphanilic acid has been used as a colorimetric reagent for Ce^{IV} by Montigne (*Bull. soc. chim.*, 1939, 6, 889). Neither the acid nor its ammonium salt precipitates thorium from neutral solution, while its sodium salt precipitates thorium quantitatively and frees it from a 100-fold excess of trivalent rare earths from solutions of p_H 2.3. These two reagents thus serve to free thorium from the rare earths of monazite after the usual treatment with oxalic acid to remove phosphoric acid, zirconium, etc.

The precipitate of thorium with sodium sulphanilate is gelatinous and corresponds probably to a hydrous oxide with varying amounts of thorium sulphanilate. The furoate, on the other hand, although gelatinous on precipitation, turns micro-crystalline after about half an hour on the water-bath and appears to be a basic salt (*vide infra*). Thus, the precipitates with both the reagents require ignition to the oxide.

EXPERIMENTAL

The preparation of thorium nitrate and rare earth nitrate solutions has been described in an earlier communication (*this Journal*, 1950, 27, 81). Other reagents employed were of the B.D.H. Analar grade.

Ammonium Furoate

Procedure.—The thorium solution containing about 0.1 g. of ThO_2 is neutralised until a drop of thymol blue gives an orange coloration, then diluted to 100 ml. The solution is heated to boiling when 100 ml. of a boiling 1% solution of ammonium furoate are added with constant stirring. A white flocculent precipitate results which on being heated on a water-bath for $\frac{1}{2}$ hour turns crystalline. The particles are, however, so small that they show often a tendency to pass through a medium pore filter. The precipitate is allowed to settle and the supernatant liquid is poured off through a Whatman 42 filter. After as much of the liquid as possible has been thus removed, the residue is stirred up with a little filter pulp to facilitate further

filtration and washing. The precipitate is washed with a hot 2% solution of ammonium nitrate, partially dried, ignited and weighed as ThO_2 . Results of thorium estimations carried out in this manner are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

ThO_2 taken.	ThO_2 estimated*.	Difference.
0.0877 g.	0.0877 g.	--
0.0438	0.0437	-0.0001 g.
0.0292	0.0293	+0.0001
0.0088	0.0086	-0.0002
0.0035	0.0035	--
0.0022	0.0021	-0.0001

*Mean of three estimations.

As little as 2.2 mg. of ThO_2 was successfully estimated.

Effect of p_n on the Precipitation of Thorium.—Since the acid precipitates the element, only partially, and since at high p_n values the rare earth elements will also precipitate, the range of complete precipitation of thorium without interference from the rare earth elements was next investigated. The results are shown in Table II.

TABLE II

Initial thorium solution.	p_n of	ThO_2 taken = 0.0877 g. Final liquid.	ThO_2 weighed.	Difference.
1.6	—	—	0.0860 g.	-0.0017 g.
1.8	3.1	3.1	0.0870	-0.0007
2.0	3.7	3.7	0.0877	--
2.3	3.8	3.8	0.0877	--
3.0	4.0	4.0	0.0878	+0.0001

Separation from Cerite Earths.—Thorium was precipitated quantitatively from solution of p_n 2.0 and higher. It was found, however, that the qualitative conditions described for the precipitation of thorium, did also free thorium from the rare earths. Results of test separations are shown in Table III.

TABLE III

ThO_2 taken.	Cerite earth oxides added.	ThO_2 obtained.	Difference.
0.0877 g.	0.1672 g.	0.0877 g.	--
0.0877	0.3344	0.0876	-0.0001 g.
0.0877	0.5016	0.0878	+0.0001
0.0877	1.1376	0.0877	--
0.0035	0.0557	0.0035	--
0.0035	0.1672	0.0035	--
0.0035	0.1756	0.0035	--
0.0035	0.3344	0.0045	+0.0010

Composition of the Precipitate.—Samples of the precipitate, washed finally with water, were dried to constant weight at $105^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ and the ratio of ThO_2 to thorium

furoate was determined by ignition of the sample to the oxide. Different samples yielded slightly varying ratios. The composition of the precipitate may be best represented by the formula $O=Th=X_2 \cdot 2H_2O$, where X represents the furoate radical, $(C_6H_5O.COO^-)$.

Estimation of Thorium in Monazite.—Thorium in a sample of monazite from Travancore, after decomposition in the usual way with concentrated sulphuric acid and a double precipitation with oxalic acid to render it free from phosphoric acid (cf. this *Journal*, *loc.cit.*), was estimated as described above. The results are shown in Table VII along with the results of estimation with sodium sulphanilate (*vide infra*).

Sodium Sulphanilate

Procedure.—The thorium solution (containing about 0.1 g. of ThO_2) is made orange or pale yellow to thymol blue, diluted to 100 ml. and heated to boiling. A boiling 10% solution of sodium sulphanilate (80 ml.) is added with stirring, and the resulting white gelatinous precipitate is further heated for five minutes with incipient boiling. After settling the precipitate is filtered through Whatman No. 42 filter and washed with hot 2% ammonium nitrate solution. The washed precipitate is partially dried, ignited and weighed. The results obtained are given in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Estimation of thorium with sodium sulphanilate.

ThO_2 taken.	ThO_2 weighed	Difference.
0.0877 g.	0.0878 g.	+0.0001 g.
0.0439	0.0440	+0.0001
0.0035	0.0035	—
0.0009	0.0009	—

* Mean of three estimations.

Thus, as little as 1 mg. of ThO_2 may be conveniently estimated.

Effect of p_H on the Precipitation of Thorium.—The precipitation of thorium under varying conditions of p_H are shown in Table V.

TABLE V

ThO_2 taken = 0.0877 g.

Initial thorium soln.	p_H of Final liquid.	ThO_2 recovered.	Difference.
2.0	—	0.0800 g.	-0.0077 g.
2.3	4.0	0.0877	—
3.0	—	0.0877	—
3.8	4.2	0.0876	-0.0001

An initial p_H of 2.3 appears to be the limit below which thorium cannot be quantitatively precipitated.

Composition of the Precipitate.—For this purpose the precipitate was finally washed with water although during this process some thorium was lost through the filter. It was then dried to a constant weight at $105^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ and weighed portions were ignited to the oxide. The ThO_2 : Th. precipitate ratios in two samples⁸ were 72.7 and 73.7 to 100

on the average. This ratio as well as the behaviour of the precipitate during washing with water indicates that the precipitate consists mainly of the hydrous oxide together with small amounts of thorium sulphaniolate. The p_H 4. of the final solution for complete precipitation of thorium, which may be compared with the value 3.91 noted for the precipitation of thorium from $\text{Th}(\text{SO}_4)_2$ in dilute H_2SO_4 by Bowles and Partridge (*Ind. Eng. Chem. Anal. Ed.*, 1937, 9, 124), also lends support to this view.

Separation from the Rare Earths.—Data on the precipitation of thorium in its relation to the p_H of the solution mark out 2.3 as the minimum p_H at which the separation from other elements may be successfully attempted. In the case of rare earths it has been noticed that co-precipitation of these elements does not occur even at a much higher p_H , 3.6. The procedure described for the estimation of thorium has been found to suit separation equally well. Results obtained in this way with varying amounts of ThO_2 as well as different ThO_2 - R_2O_3 ratios are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI

ThO_2 taken.	R_2O_3 added.	ThO_2 obtained.	Difference.
0.0877 g.	0.1672 g.	0.0877	—
0.0877	0.3344	0.0878	+0.0001 g.
0.0877	0.5016	0.0876	-0.0001
0.0877	0.7524	0.0877	—
0.0877	1.6720	0.0876	-0.0001
0.0877	2.6752	0.0877	—
0.0439	3.0016	0.0439	—
0.0439	3.5112	0.0438	-0.0001
0.0035	0.3511	0.0036	+0.0001

The reagent thus frees as little as 3.5 mg. of ThO_2 from a hundred-fold excess of ceria-earth oxides in one operation.

Estimation of Thoria in Monazite.—Results of estimation of thoria in monazite employing (i) *m*-nitrobenzoic acid, (ii) ammonium furoate and (iii) sodium sulphaniolate are shown in Table VII. The values shown under *m*-nitrobenzoic acid are those obtained on double precipitation.

TABLE VII

No.	Monazite taken.	% ThO_2 employing		Sodium sulphaniolate
		<i>m</i> -Nitrobenzoic acid.	Ammonium furoate.	
1	20 ml.	8.20	8.20	8.10
2	20	8.19	8.10	8.19
3	20	8.18	8.18	8.20
4	10	8.20	8.20	8.17
5	10	8.23	8.20	8.19
6	10	8.19	8.21	8.20
	ean.	8.20	8.18	8.17